

A Survey of Formal Methods for Autonomous Robots - List of Identified Tools

Atef Azaiez¹,
Marie Farrell²

¹ Faculty of Science and Tech., Norwegian University of Life Sciences, Ås, Norway
`{atef.azaiez,david.anisi}@nmbu.no`

² Department of Computer Science, University of Manchester, Manchester, UK
`marie.farrell@manchester.ac.uk`

³ School of Computer Science, University of Nottingham, Nottingham, UK
`matt.luckcuck@nottingham.ac.uk`

ID	Tool	Nº Recorded Uses
1	UPPAAL(-SMC)	23
2	PRISM	12
3	NuSMV/NuXmv	12
4	SPIN	10
5	MCMAS	6
6	Maude	5
7	Matlab/Simulink(SDV)	4
8	CafeOBJ	4
9	KeYmaera	4
10	TuLiP	3
11	RoboTool/Chart	3
12	Z3 SMT Solver	2
13	TLC	2
14	STORM	2
15	SpaceEx	2
16	PHAVer	2
17	PESSOA	2
18	LTLMoP	2
19	Isabelle(/SACM)	2
20	HyTech	2
21	FDR	2
22	BrahmsToPromela	2
23	Brahms	2
24	Ariadne	2
25	AJPF	2
26	Why3	1
27	VIVE/SESA	1
28	ViSpec	1
29	VIPARS	1

30	VeriNet	1
31	VerifAI	1
32	UPMurphi	1
33	TINA	1
34	TAPA	1
35	Spot	1
36	Spark	1
37	SMOF	1
38	SMACH	1
39	Slugs	1
40	SLCS	1
41	SEECER	1
42	Scenic	1
43	salma	1
44	Rodin	1
45	R2U2	1
46	ProB, TLC and Alloy	1
47	PCIS	1
48	PAT	1
49	Other	1
50	NANESVerify	1
51	Mc-COGWED	1
52	MCAPL	1
53	MARIA	1
54	Marabou	1
55	KnowLang (language, not really a tool)	1
56	jABC - java	1
57	Hydra	1
58	Gazebo Simulator	1
59	Electrum	1
60	EBMC	1
61	Dfinder	1
62	DeepReach	1
63	Daikon	1
64	Dafny	1
65	CPPCC	1
66	CPL	1
67	CORA	1
68	CoPilot	1
69	COMICS	1
70	CLawZ	1
71	CBMC	1
72	Breach	1

73	Averest	1
74	AltaRica	1
75	Alloy	1